

Real-Time Reconfiguration for Large-Scale Distribution Networks: A Multi-Opening Linear Approach

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Abstract—Distribution network reconfiguration (DNR) is a core operational tool in modern distribution grids, enabling fast, topology-based control to reduce losses, improve voltage profiles, and alleviate overloads in the presence of variability introduced by distributed energy resources. This paper proposes a DNR solution based on a new linear model of branch currents when a set of lines is opened simultaneously, integrated into a graph-theoretic framework. With this model, network losses can be estimated for any set of simultaneous line openings, avoiding the need to solve a power-flow for each tree under analysis. The method proceeds in two phases, both leveraging the same linear model: the first obtains a minimum spanning tree from single-opening estimates on the meshed network, thereby obtaining an initial set of candidate branches to open; the second refines that set by evaluating alternative multiple-opening branch sets with the same linear model. With the proposed methodology, only one power-flow solve of the initial meshed network is required. Tests carried out on networks of up to 10 000 nodes show significant reductions in losses and very low execution times, supporting real-time applicability at a scale at which most existing approaches have not been demonstrated.

Index Terms—Distribution network reconfiguration, multi-opening current-based linear model, real-time operation, minimum spanning tree.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distribution network reconfiguration (DNR) is a key operational tool to improve efficiency and resilience. By changing the status of system ties and sectionalizing switches while preserving radial operation, operators can redirect power flows to meet operational objectives—such as reducing technical losses, relieving thermal constraints, or enhancing voltage profiles. These capabilities that are increasingly critical given the variability of modern distribution networks [1], [2].

Since the DNR problem involves finding an optimal switching configuration under operating constraints, as might be the preservation of radiality; bus-voltage limits; and thermal/ampacity ratings, it can be observed from an optimization viewpoint as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming

(MINLP) problem, binary variables encoding the open/closed states of switches, and continuous variables including electrical magnitudes (voltages, currents, and power flows). The main drawback of this approach, as stated in [3], is related to the number of feasible radial configurations, which grows exponentially with network size, making exhaustive search impractical, even for moderately sized feeders.

The most common objective function in the DNR problem is related to technical loss reduction, since it is generally assumed that this approach leads to: (i) pulling terminal bus voltages closer to their nominal values [4], and (ii) producing more balanced load profiles across feeders when switching is the only available control strategy [5]. This premise is supported by previous work that highlights the use of loss-oriented reconfiguration to implicitly improve voltage profiles and feeder consumption balance. Moreover, since total losses can be expressed as a weighted sum of squared voltage differences between branches, the loss minimization and enhanced voltage levels are aligned [6].

In modern distribution systems, the practical application of DNR increasingly requires real-time decision-making in networks that are becoming larger in size and more complex in operation. This trend amplifies the importance of computationally efficient techniques that can be scaled to the high dimensionality of realistic feeders within operational timeframes. Hence, there is a pressing need for methods that are scalable with respect to network size, capable of delivering fast and accurate estimations of the impact of switching actions, and thus suitable for real-time deployment. Addressing this challenge is central to the contribution of this work, which proposes a reconfiguration strategy designed to combine computational efficiency with sufficient precision to be effective in large-scale practical scenarios.

The DNR has been widely addressed in the literature, [7], [8]. As summarized by Rahimipour Behbahani et al. [8], these approaches can be broadly classified into five main categories: classical methods, heuristic methods, metaheuristic methods, hybrid methods and machine learning-based methods. Classical techniques rely on mathematical reformulations, often transforming the problem through some approximations to

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ensure tractability [2], [9], [3]. Heuristic approaches exploit problem-specific rules to generate feasible solutions with reduced computational effort [10], [11]. Metaheuristic algorithms, including genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, and simulated annealing, provide more general-purpose, nature-inspired iterative strategies that balance exploration and exploitation of the solution space [12], [13]. Hybrid methods aim to combine the strengths of two or more categories, for example, heuristic rules with metaheuristic algorithms, to enhance convergence and robustness [14]. Finally, machine learning-based techniques, such as artificial neural networks and reinforcement learning, have recently emerged as promising candidates, especially for dynamic DNR, due to their ability to make decisions almost instantaneously after offline training [15].

For the particular case of heuristic methods, in which the strategy proposed in this paper can be framed, several approaches can be distinguished, such as the optimal flow pattern method [4] and branch exchange (BE) methods [10], [11]. Branch exchange methods are a classical, radiality-preserving heuristic for DNR. These techniques start from a feasible (suboptimal) radial topology and iteratively improve it through local exchanges between an open line and a closed one, always maintaining radiality. In practice, only a small neighbourhood around the temporarily closed tie is typically considered when selecting candidates. While feasibility checks are straightforward and radiality is preserved by construction, these methods can be computationally demanding on large networks, as each candidate switch may require one or more power-flow calculations and many iterations may be necessary [8], [16]. These types of solutions, whose advantages and limitations are well-known in the literature [7], [8], typically focus on quickly solving the reconfiguration problem by relaxing the nonlinearity of the problem and, therefore, at the expense of obtaining local minima. This loss of accuracy is especially significant in large networks. In addition, the solution achieved is often heavily influenced by the initial starting topology considered.

The method proposed in this paper follows the BE paradigm, initially obtaining a suboptimal baseline through a minimum-spanning-tree (MST) algorithm and improving this solution via BE. For this reason, the case studies include a comparison with representative MST–BE approaches from the literature. Li et al. [17] propose a three-stage process. First, an MST is built on the meshed network using edge weights derived from voltage-drop information. Second, local screening based on voltage-drop limits reduces the set of neighbouring candidates around the closed tie. Finally, a correction step explores neighbour exchanges to further reduce losses. Ahmadi et al. [6] also construct an MST baseline and refine it with BE, evaluating neighbouring exchanges using line–outage distribution factors that linearize the impact on branch currents when a single line is opened; using these distribution factors avoids performing multiple power-flow calculations during the exchange evaluation.

In this regard, this work presents a real-time DNR method-

ology based on the calculation of loss sensitivities for a fast estimation of technical losses for any set of line openings. The reconfiguration is addressed as an MST problem with sensitivity-based edge weights to obtain a baseline radial configuration. The proposed algorithm applies a Multi-Opening Branch Exchange (MOBE) refinement to improve the initial losses while preserving radiality and ensuring computational efficiency. The proposed strategy achieves low-losses configurations with reduced runtime, suitable for real-time application to large, highly meshed electrical networks, preserving in all cases radial operation and avoiding repeated calculation of customary power-flow solutions; in fact, only a single power-flow solve of the meshed base state is required throughout the entire approach. The main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- Development of a linear model to estimate branch currents and power losses for any set of simultaneously opened lines.
- Application of this model to solve the DNR problem through a two-phase methodology: an MST-based baseline and a novel MOBE refinement that captures interdependencies among multiple openings.
- Validation on very large-scale networks (up to 10,000 nodes), demonstrating significant loss reductions and execution times compatible with real-time operation at scales where most existing approaches have not been validated.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the proposed methodology, outlining the current-based loss-sensitivity model used to predict post-switching currents and losses for any set of line openings; the construction of MST-based edge weights; and the MOBE refinement. Section III presents different case studies on standard benchmark feeders, reporting loss reduction and computational efficiency, including a comparative analysis with various state-of-the-art techniques. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This section details the proposed real-time DNR framework that couples a linear, physics-based loss-sensitivity model with graph algorithms. This methodology involves the following steps, as depicted in Fig. 1.

A. Loss Sensitivities

For a given electrical network with N buses and B branches, and a specific initial load/generation scenario, a sensitivity-based model is derived, enabling the estimation of branch currents and therefore active-power losses, after a certain number of lines in the system are opened.

The bus-admittance matrix, which relates bus voltages and injected currents, can be obtained as

$$Y_{\text{bus}} = A^T Y_b A + Y_{\text{load}}. \quad (1)$$

where:

- A is the network incidence matrix, dimension $B \times N$,
- $Y_b = \text{diag}(y_1, \dots, y_B)$ is a diagonal matrix of dimension $B \times B$ including branch series admittances, and

Fig. 1. Proposed methodological process

- Y_{load} denotes the nodal admittance matrix taking into account the load connected to the network. Y_{load} is a diagonal matrix of dimension $N \times N$ whose n -th entry is the equivalent load admittance at bus n with the load S_n , i.e., $y_n = S_n^*/U_n^2$, evaluated using the bus voltages obtained from the power-flow solution computed for the fully meshed network.

This matrix can be partitioned as follows.

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_s \\ I_r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{ss} & Y_{sr} \\ Y_{rs} & Y_{rr} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_s \\ U_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where s denotes the slack bus and r the remaining buses. In (2), U_s is the voltage of the slack bus and U_r is a vector that contains the voltages in the remaining buses. Furthermore, I_s and I_r denote the corresponding injected currents. The previous expression can be linearized around any operating point with fixed slack voltage ($\Delta U_s = 0$), yielding the following incremental equation:

$$\Delta U_r = Y_{rr}^{-1} \Delta I_r \quad (3)$$

Additionally, currents along the branches, J , might be calculated using Ohm's law as

$$J = Y_b A U \quad (4)$$

with $U^T = [U_s \ U_r^T]$ containing the voltages of all buses. The incremental counterpart of the previous expression, assuming $\Delta U_s = 0$, is presented below:

$$\Delta J = Y_b A_r \Delta U_r = Y_b A_r Y_{rr}^{-1} \Delta I_r \quad (5)$$

where A_r is the reduced incidence matrix, removing the column corresponding to the slack bus. From the above results, the branch-current sensitivity matrix is defined as

$$S_{J,I} = Y_b A_r Y_{rr}^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

so that

$$\Delta J = S_{J,I} \Delta I_r \quad (7)$$

One of the main challenges in DNR is that every possible radial tree corresponds to a different electrical model, since the nodal admittance matrix changes with each switching action.

This makes the problem computationally demanding, as the Jacobian matrix for the power-flow calculation needs to be recomputed for each topology.

To overcome this issue, an approach is adopted in this work inspired by the N-1 security analysis in transmission systems. Line openings are emulated as fictitious-current injections of equal magnitude and opposite direction in the corresponding terminal nodes. These currents do not represent physical flows, but rather a mathematical construct that allows one to preserve Kirchhoff's current law while evaluating the impact of the topology change.

For a given branch connecting nodes i and j , as shown in the illustrative example included in Fig.2, the fictitious current J_{ij}^f is defined so that the effective current through the opened line is zero. Using the previously derived sensitivity matrices, the condition can be expressed as

$$J_{ij}^f = J_{ij}^0 + S_{ij,i} J_{ij}^f - S_{ij,j} J_{ij}^f \quad (8)$$

where J_{ij}^0 is the previous current through the line (assuming a fully-meshed configuration in the problem under consideration) and $S_{ij,i}, S_{ij,j}$ are the sensitivity coefficients that relate nodal current injections in buses i and j with the flow in the branch (i, j) . This equation provides a unique value of J_{ij}^f , which might be used to compute the new branch currents throughout the rest of the network. The authors in [6] propose an approach focused on dealing with single-line openings by using the above reasoning. The strategy presented in this work extends it by enabling the estimation of currents and losses for sets of simultaneously opened lines, capturing

Fig. 2. Line opening emulation.

interdependencies between multiple openings, which is not addressed in [6].

This formulation can be extended to multiple simultaneous line openings and not just a single branch opening. Thus, as it is necessary to open $K = B - N + 1$ branches to obtain a radial configuration from a meshed network with N nodes and B branches, K fictitious currents are introduced, each of them complying with what is already outlined in Fig.2. The opening of more than one branch involves new fictitious current injections in more than two nodes, so (8) becomes:

$$J_{ij}^f = J_{ij}^0 + \sum_{km \in K} S_{ij,k} J_{km}^f - S_{ij,m} J_{km}^f \quad \forall ij \in K \quad (9)$$

A matrix formulation of (9) results in:

$$J_o^f = J_o^0 + S_{J_o I}^f (A_o^f)^\top J_o^f \quad (10)$$

where $S_{J_o I}^f$ and A_o^f are submatrices of sensitivities and incidence matrices, respectively, corresponding to the selected open branches. Operating in (10), it is possible to compute the set of K fictitious currents by solving the linear system (11):

$$(\mathbb{I} - S_{J_o I}^f (A_o^f)^\top) J_o^f = J_o^0 \quad (11)$$

where \mathbb{I} denotes the identity matrix.

It should be remarked that when the chosen set of lines to be opened leads to a spanning tree for the considered network, the non-singularity of the involved matrix $Q = (\mathbb{I} - S_{J_o I}^f (A_o^f)^\top)$ is guaranteed.

Once the currents J_o^f are computed by solving (11), it is possible to deduce the currents through all closed lines J_c using (7), being ΔI_r defined by the fictitious currents as schemed in Fig. 2, that is:

$$J_c = J_c^0 + S_{J_c I} A_c^T J_o^f \quad (12)$$

where $S_{J_c I}$ and A_c are submatrices of sensitivities and incidence matrices, respectively, associated to the closed branches. Finally, the total active losses are computed as follows:

$$P_{\text{loss}} = J_c^T R_D J_c \quad (13)$$

where R_D is a diagonal matrix with branch resistances of closed lines.

The proposed linear sensitivity-based electrical model allows the post-switching branch currents and associated losses to be calculated using precomputed terms. Indeed, for any set of line openings the fictitious currents are calculated by solving (11), the closed-branch currents are then obtained using (12), and the power losses are finally evaluated through (13). The above operations, in addition to being linear, only require computing the branch-current sensitivity matrix S_{JI} for the meshed network once, precalculating the system state J^0 for the starting point, and calculating the inverse of a small matrix Q of size $B - N + 1$ that changes with the set of open lines to be evaluated. Note that a single AC power-flow solution is enough for the whole approach, so this estimation of losses

is much faster than iterative power-flow calculations, enabling real-time screening of many switching candidates and forming the foundation for both the MST baseline and the subsequent MOBE refinement.

B. Minimum Spanning Tree

The proposed algorithm for DNR starts with the calculation of a radial baseline configuration of the network. For this purpose, a MST algorithm is considered, where a certain weight is associated with each branch on the basis of the power losses that the system would experience if only this line, ℓ , was open, namely $P_{\text{loss}}(\ell)$, calculated through the previously described sensitivity model. Using these power losses, the corresponding line weights w_ℓ are calculated as follows:

$$w_\ell = M - P_{\text{loss}}(\ell) \quad (14)$$

where M is a large constant. The implemented MST algorithm selects the $N - 1$ branches that minimize $\sum w_\ell$, that is, minimize power losses in the obtained radial network.

In this work, standard MST algorithms (e.g., Kruskal [18] or Prim [19]) are considered. A known limitation of the baseline MST stage is that interdependencies among multiple simultaneous openings are not captured, since edge scores are derived from one-at-a-time openings.

C. Multi-Opening Branch Exchange

In order to refine the initial MST baseline, in this work, a recursive, global MOBE procedure is proposed. Starting from a radial configuration of the network, one of the open lines is closed to create a fundamental cycle in the corresponding graph. Then, using the sensitivity model, all admissible line exchanges obtained by opening any edge in that cycle are evaluated. The modification that most reduces the power losses (if any) is selected. Finally, the procedure is repeated until no further improvement is observed.

The theoretical basis behind the proposed approach lies in the fact that when a non-tree edge is added to a spanning tree, a unique fundamental cycle is created. Removing any edge on that cycle restores a spanning tree, whereas removing any other edge breaks connectivity while the cycle persists [20]. The different steps of the proposed MOBE algorithm are detailed below, as represented in the flowchart in Fig. 3.

- 1) Let the *Open Lines Set (OLS)* be the list of lines that are open in the current solution (initially, those in the MST baseline). The *Switchable Lines Set (SLS)* collects the lines subject to exchange whose evaluation will be performed; initialize it as $SLS \leftarrow OLS$. Set $P_{\text{loss}}^{\text{min}}$ to the losses of the MST configuration.
- 2) Pop one line ℓ from SLS and temporarily close it in the current radial tree. This creates exactly one simple (fundamental) cycle. The only admissible candidates whose opening preserves connectivity and radially are the edges on the unique path between the endpoints (i, j) of ℓ in the current tree. Define the *Alternative Lines Set ALS*(ℓ) as the set of edges constituting that path.

Fig. 3. MOBE flowchart

- 3) For each candidate a in $ALS(\ell)$, consider the whole topology obtained by replacing ℓ with a in OLS; denote its losses by $P_{\text{loss}}^{(\ell \rightarrow a)}$ and evaluate them with the sensitivity-based model using (11)–(13), which allows handling multiple simultaneous line openings and avoids any power-flow execution.
- 4) Let a^* be the candidate in $ALS(\ell)$ with the smallest losses. If $P_{\text{loss}}^{(\ell \rightarrow a^*)} < P_{\text{loss}}^{\min}$, accept the exchange: keep ℓ closed and a^* opened—i.e., exchange ℓ and a^* in OLS—update $P_{\text{loss}}^{\min} \leftarrow P_{\text{loss}}^{(\ell \rightarrow a^*)}$, and append a^* to the end of SLS for later testing.
- 5) If SLS is not empty, return to Step 2; otherwise, terminate.

As stated previously in this paper, the main limitation of the initial MST baseline is that interdependency among multiple simultaneous openings is not captured, since edge weights are based on one-at-a-time openings. In the MOBE refinement, these interactions are taken into account. This context-aware evaluation is able to capture multi-opening interdependencies, improving loss estimates while avoiding global reweighting and additional MST computations.

III. CASE STUDIES

To assess the performance of the proposed DNR methodology, a series of simulations have been conducted on various distribution networks. The objective of these tests is to demonstrate the capability of the proposed methodology to reduce network losses while preserving radiality and operational constraints, as well as to evaluate its computational efficiency with different network sizes.

A. Benchmark

The methodology has been applied to the following benchmark distribution networks: 33-node [11], 69-node [21], 84-node [22], 118-node [23], 137-node [24], 205-node [24], 409-node [25], 873-node [26], and 10476-node [26]. These networks span a wide range of sizes and complexities, allowing a comprehensive assessment of the proposed approach under realistic operating conditions.

B. Validation of the Linear Sensitivity Model

This subsection is aimed to assess the accuracy of the linear sensitivity-based model described in Section II for the estimation of branch currents and power losses in radial configurations when compared to the exact values obtained from an AC power-flow solution.

This validation is performed on the 33-node test network. Given the number of possible radial topologies, a Monte Carlo approach is adopted. A total of 1000 random radial configurations are generated by randomly opening lines while preserving radiality and connectivity. For each topology, the following steps are performed:

- The linear sensitivity model is used to estimate the branch currents and total power losses.
- An exact AC power-flow calculation is performed on the same radial topology to obtain the actual branch currents and power losses.

To quantify the estimation error, the weighted absolute percentage error (WAPE) is used for both branch currents and total active power losses. WAPE avoids the distortion caused by near-zero values, which may arise in the current magnitudes of some branches and can plague the classical mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)

$$WAPE = \frac{\sum_b |y_b - \hat{y}_b|}{\sum_b |y_b|} \times 100, \quad (15)$$

where y_b and \hat{y}_b denote the real values from the AC power-flow and the estimates provided by the linear sensitivity-based model, respectively. For branch currents, the summations run

over all closed branches of the evaluated radial topology, yielding a single aggregated error per configuration. For total active power losses, the same metric is applied to the single loss value of each topology; therefore, in this case, WAPE is equivalent to the absolute percentage error.

The 1000 random radial configurations are sorted from highest to lowest total losses. Fig. 4 shows the resulting WAPE for branch-current magnitudes and total losses along this ranking. As expected for a linearization around the fully meshed operating point, larger errors appear in configurations with higher losses, which typically reflect more pronounced changes in power-flow patterns and therefore larger deviations from the base operating point, whereas lower-loss configurations are estimated more accurately. The solutions delivered by the proposed DNR methodology consistently fall within this region, which supports the sensitivity-based model suitability for the reconfiguration process.

Fig. 4. WAPE for branch-current magnitudes (orange) and total active power losses (blue) over 1,000 random radial configurations of the 33-node network, ranked by decreasing true losses.

C. Results and discussion

The results obtained with the proposed methodology are compared in terms of loss reduction and computational efficiency with two state-of-the-art methods based on the application of MST and BE solution refinements previously described in Section II [6], [17]. The comparison, shown in Table I, also reports the losses of the initial configuration for each network and includes the best-known solution where available, highlighting the advantages of the proposed approach in achieving reduced-loss configurations while maintaining a low computational effort even for large-scale networks.

Regarding computation time, columns in Table I are defined below:

- t_{pf} — Power-flow computation. Time to run the only AC power-flow required by the proposed methodology to obtain the operating point in the meshed configuration.
- t_{sm} — Sensitivity-model build. Time to compute the sensitivity-based model (matrix S_{JI}).
- t_{MST} — MST baseline. Time to construct the network graph, compute branch weights (loss estimates for single openings), and execute the MST algorithm to obtain the initial radial baseline.
- t_{MOBE} — MOBE refinement. Time to apply the MOBE procedure previously described until the final solution is reached.
- t_{total} — Total computation time. Calculated as:

$$t_{total} = t_{sm} + t_{pf} + t_{MST} + t_{MOBE} \quad (16)$$

For comparison purposes related to computation time, all experiments were executed on a laptop equipped with an Intel® Core™ Ultra 7 155H (1.40 GHz) CPU and 32 GB RAM. The algorithms are implemented in Python, using networkx library for graph operations [27]. For the MST stage, Kruskal’s [18] and Prim’s [19] algorithms were tested, ultimately adopting the latter due to slightly faster runtimes in the benchmarks considered.

In light of the results presented in Table I, the following comments are in order:

- Compared to Li [17], the proposed methodology for DNR achieves lower losses and shorter runtimes for the entire set of tested feeders. Moreover, for the 118-node network,

TABLE I
LOSSES AND RUNTIMES COMPARISON FOR TESTES NETWORKS.

#Nodes / #Loops	Losses (kW)					Time (s)					Li [17]	Ahmadi [6]
	Initial	Best-known	Proposed	Li [17]	Ahmadi [6]	Proposed						
						t_{pf}	t_{sm}	t_{MST}	t_{MOBE}	t_{total}		
33 / 5	202.68	139.55	139.55	139.55	139.98	0.018	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.023	0.250	0.045
69 / 5	69.90	30.10	30.10	32.37	32.60	0.012	0.005	0.002	0.004	0.022	0.697	0.076
84 / 13	531.83	469.78	469.96	469.78	469.96	0.014	0.005	0.002	0.004	0.025	0.573	0.156
118 / 15	1297.56	870.31	888.66	—	892.27	0.019	0.011	0.003	0.009	0.041	—	1.295
137 / 12	139.79	60.20	60.20	66.46	65.19	0.019	0.011	0.003	0.011	0.044	3.399	1.438
205 / 20	209.69	85.11	85.11	103.91	91.03	0.026	0.021	0.005	0.027	0.079	7.174	5.728
409 / 43	419.38	166.23	166.91	178.82	188.95	0.053	0.065	0.013	0.172	0.303	35.746	30.754
873 / 27	1496.44	—	457.08	459.58	461.08	0.106	0.235	0.027	0.075	0.443	9.093	34.504
10476 / 252	17373.88	—	8896.96	8949.84	9170.38	1.228	34.526	2.545	185.555	223.853	1299.083	32643.443

Li’s method did not provide a feasible radial configuration under the imposed operating limits.

- Regarding the method in [6], the proposed strategy attains lower losses and shorter runtimes on the reported benchmarks. When implementing [6], the measured runtimes are substantially larger than those reported in the original paper, while the same percentage loss reduction reported by the authors is observed (e.g., about 47% on the 10 476-node network). This is explained by the need—stated in that approach—to recompute the sensitivity factors (8) for each tie configuration, which requires inverting the modified bus-admittance matrix (see (6)) within the outer branch–exchange loop; the cost of this inversion grows with network size and dominates the total runtime on large feeders. In contrast, the MOBE methodology evaluates candidate exchanges using precomputed sensitivity-based operators, avoiding per-tie bus-admittance matrix inversions and thereby achieving lower runtimes while preserving solution quality.

To validate the accuracy of the proposed linear sensitivity-based model, Table II presents the WAPE obtained for both branch currents and power losses when evaluating the final radial configuration achieved by the methodology. These errors are computed by comparing the estimates from the linear model against the exact values obtained from an AC power-flow solution of the resulting radial topology, as described in Section III.B. As observed, the estimation errors remain very low across all tested networks, confirming that the linear model provides a sufficiently accurate approximation for guiding the reconfiguration process while avoiding multiple power-flow calculations.

Finally, Fig. 5 compares the bus voltage distributions across all tested networks, comparing the initial radial configuration with the one obtained by the proposed DNR method. Although the optimization target is loss reduction, the proposed configurations exhibit a systematic rise in voltages, leading to an improved voltage profile in all case studies while complying with the 0.93 p.u. lower limit. This observation

TABLE II
ESTIMATION ERRORS FOR TESTED NETWORKS.

#Nodes	$WAPE_{currents}$ (%)	$WAPE_{loss}$ (%)
33	0.0812	0.1643
69	0.0261	0.0860
84	0.0199	0.0370
118	0.0278	0.0448
137	0.0325	0.1067
205	0.0298	0.0907
409	0.0311	0.0997
873	0.0009	0.0020
10,476	0.0005	0.0005

is consistent with the working hypothesis stated earlier—that loss-oriented reconfiguration tends to improve voltage profiles—even though voltages are not explicitly optimized in the procedure. Overall, these results validate the proposed methodology, outperforming state-of-the-art approaches.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a real-time methodology for DNR that couples a linear loss-sensitivity model with a graph-theoretic approach. Using a single AC power-flow solution for the meshed base topology, a novel theoretical approach is presented in the form of a linear system of equations to systematically compute fictitious current injections that emulate line openings and provide estimates of post-switching branch currents and losses for any set of simultaneously opened lines. These loss estimates define edge weights for an MST algorithm, yielding a radial baseline, which is then refined through a MOBE procedure that evaluates exchanges on the cycle induced by temporarily closing a candidate line. In doing so, interdependencies among jointly opened lines are explicitly considered while avoiding repeated power-flow computations.

Extensive tests on standard benchmarks with increasing size show that the proposed approach consistently achieves reduced-loss configurations with very low runtimes. MOBE

Fig. 5. Boxplots of bus voltages (pu) before (gray) and after (green) reconfiguration across the benchmark networks

attains a favorable trade-off between solution quality (loss reduction) and computational cost, and its effectiveness is demonstrated on large-scale networks, a scale at which most existing approaches have not been validated.

In summary, the method preserves radiality at all times, avoids repeated power-flow solutions (only one is required for the meshed base state), and scales well across network sizes. Limitations include the heuristic nature of the approach (no global optimality certificate) and that the sensitivities, while yielding satisfactory results, are exact only under a constant-current load model. Future work will extend the framework to multiobjective optimization with explicit voltage and thermal margins and to time-coupled and uncertainty-aware reconfiguration.

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